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Elastic and thermo-acoustic study of YM intermetallics

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The work involves estimation of elastic, ultrasonic and thermo-physical properties of YM (Y: Yttrium, M=Zn, Cu, Ag) intermetallics at 300 K. Initially, second order elastic constants and elastic modulus of chosen intermetallics are determined in temperature range 300K-1200K under potential model approach. Later, the ultrasonic velocities are calculated using second order elastic constants and densities for wave propagation along $\langle 100 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystallographic directions. Additionally, Debye temperature, specific heat at constant volume, thermal conductivity and thermal relaxation time are also calculated. The analysis reveals that compound YCu incorporates better mechanical and thermal properties than the other two compounds.

Keywords: Intermetallics, elastic properties; ultrasonic velocity; thermal relaxation time; thermal conductivity.

Introduction

Intermetallics are combination of materials of two or more types of metal atoms that differ in structure in comparison to the constituent metals. Binary rare-earth intermetallics have many practical applications due to their superior mechanical, thermo-dynamical, electrical and magnetic properties in comparison to ordinary metals¹⁻³. These materials possess high strength, ductility, melting point, good corrosion resistance and low specific heat which make them important for commercial applications. Rare-earth intermetallics YCu, YZn, and YAg are B2 structured (CsCl-type) crystalline material^{1,2}.

The elastic and mechanical behaviour of YCu, YZn, and YAg intermetallics have been reported in literature which is based on *ab initio* calculation¹. Similarly elastic and mechanical properties of YAg, YCu, YRh intermetallics have also been studied using first principle calculations². The Mechanical, electronic and thermo-dynamic properties of AgRE (RE: Rare earth metals) ScZn, YZn and YAg intermetallics are reported elsewhere⁴⁻⁶. Chen *et al.*⁷ determines intrinsic characteristics of dislocations in ductile YCu and YAg intermetallic by *ab initio* density functional theory. The

survey of literatures indicate that, in spite of technological importance of these rare earth intermetallics, a systematic theoretical study of structural, elastic, ultrasonic and thermo-physical properties of these materials, is still needed for future applications.

In the present work, elastic, ultrasonic and thermo-physical properties of YM (M=Zn, Cu, Ag) intermetallics are illustrated. The second order elastic constants (SOECs) are calculated using potential model approach in temperature range 300-1200 K. After that, we determined the elastic moduli (bulk modulus-*B*, Young's modulus-*Y*, shear modulus-*G*, Lamé modulus- Poisson's ratio- σ) and anisotropy (*A*) of chosen intermetallics. Later, the ultrasonic velocities along three crystallographic directions ($\langle 100 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$) and thermo-physical properties (Debye temperature, specific heat at constant volume, thermal conductivity and thermal relaxation time) have been determined.

Theory

According to Cauchy's definition, the second order strain derivative of elastic energy density provides SOECs of the crystalline material.

$$C_{IJ} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial \eta_I \partial \eta_J}; \text{ I or J } = 1, 2, \dots, 6 \quad (1)$$

Where, F is elastic energy density and η is strain. The free energy density in square terms of strain for cubic structured material can be written as⁸:

$$F = \frac{1}{2!} C_{IJ} \eta_I \eta_J$$

$$F = (1/2) [C_{11} (\eta_{11}^2 + \eta_{22}^2 + \eta_{33}^2) + C_{12} (\eta_{11}\eta_{22} + \eta_{11}\eta_{33} + \eta_{22}\eta_{33}) + 2 C_{44} (\eta_{12}^2 + \eta_{23}^2 + \eta_{31}^2)] \quad (2)$$

Therefore, crystal symmetry of cubic crystals leads three SOECs (C_{11} , C_{12} and C_{44}). The elastic energy density (F) at finite temperature (T) is sum of energy density at 0 K and increase in energy (vibrational part of energy density) with enhancement in temperature⁹ by amount T .

$$F = F^0 + F^V \quad (3)$$

Where, F^0 is the internal energy of unit volume of the crystal when all atoms (ions) are at rest on their lattice point and F^V is the vibrational free energy density. Thus the SOECs can be separated into two parts.

$$C_{IJ} = C_{IJ}^0 + C_{IJ}^V \quad (4)$$

Here, C_{IJ}^0 and C_{IJ}^V are the static and vibrational parts of these SOECs and are equal to second order strain derivative of F^0 and F^V respectively. The quantity C_{IJ}^0 possesses a constant value while C_{IJ}^V varies with temperature as vibrational free energy density depends on temperature. Both these quantities can be determined with the formulations given elsewhere¹⁰. The estimation of SOECs requires only the lattice parameter (a) and non-linearity parameter which is determined under equilibrium condition. The evaluation of bulk modulus (B), Shear modulus (G), Young's modulus (Y), Lamé modulus (λ & μ), Poisson ratio (σ) and anisotropy (A) are directly/indirectly based on SOECs. The expression to compute B , G , Y , σ , λ , μ are given in literature^{11,12}.

There are three types of ultrasonic velocities for each direction of propagation in cubic crystals, one is longitudinal velocity (V_L) and other two are shear velocities (V_{S1} and V_{S2})^{13, 14}. The expressions for velocities are as follows:

Along $\langle 100 \rangle$ crystallographic direction

$$V_L = \left\{ \frac{C_{11}}{d} \right\}^{1/2}; V_{S1} = V_{S2} = \left\{ \frac{C_{44}}{d} \right\}^{1/2} \quad (5a)$$

Along $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystallographic direction

$$V_L = \left\{ \frac{C_{11} + 2C_{12} + 4C_{44}}{3d} \right\}^{1/2}; V_{S1} = V_{S2} = \left\{ \frac{C_{11} - C_{12} + 2C_{44}}{3d} \right\}^{1/2} \quad (5b)$$

Along $\langle 110 \rangle$ crystallographic direction

$$V_L = \left\{ \frac{C_{11} + C_{12} + 2C_{44}}{2d} \right\}^{1/2}; V_{S1} = \left\{ \frac{C_{44}}{d} \right\}^{1/2}; V_{S2} = \left\{ \frac{C_{11} - C_{12}}{d} \right\}^{1/2} \quad (5c)$$

The density of CsCl-structured material can be determined by following expression¹⁵.

$$d = \frac{M_w n}{N_A a^3} \quad (6)$$

Where, M_w , N_A , a and n are molecular weight, Avagadro number, lattice parameter and number of atoms per unit cell, respectively. Debye average velocity is an important parameter in the low temperature physics because it is related to elastic constants through ultrasonic velocities. Expression for Debye average velocity is given in literature¹⁶. Debye temperature (T_D) is indirectly related to elastic constants through Debye average velocity¹⁷.

On the propagation of ultrasonic wave, the thermal distribution of phonon will be disturbed. The time taken for re-establishment of equilibrium of the thermal phonons is called the thermal relaxation time (τ) It is a relation among thermal conductivity, specific heat and Debye average velocity.

Here, τ is thermal relaxation time

$$T = 3k/C_V V_D^2 \quad (7)$$

The quantities k and C_V are the thermal conductivity and specific heat per unit volume of the material. The specific heat per unit volume is function of T_D/T and can be taken from literature^{17,18}. The thermal conductivity of CsCl type material can be determined by following expression¹⁹:

$$k = \frac{\hat{A} M_w T_D^3 \delta^3}{\gamma^2 T n^{2/3}} \quad (8)$$

Where, \hat{A} is a constant; δ^3 is volume per atom; γ is Grüneisen parameter; T_D is the Debye temperature. The constant \hat{A} is function of Grüneisen parameter and is given by following expression.

$$\hat{A} = \frac{2.43 \times 10^{-8}}{1 - 0.514/\gamma + 0.228/\gamma^2}; \gamma = \frac{3(3C_{11}^2 - 4C_{44}^2)}{2(C_{11}^2 + 2C_{44}^2)} \quad (9)$$

Results and Discussion

The lattice parameters (a) of YZn, YCu and YAg intermetallics are 3.579Å, 3.478Å and 3.641Å respectively¹. The non-linearity parameters (b) for the chosen intermetallics are found 0.265Å, 0.305Å, and 0.255 Å respectively under equilibrium condition. These lattice and non-linearity parameters are used for the determination of SOECs of YM intermetallics at 300-1200 K. The obtained SOECs are depicted in Table 1 and Fig. 1. Elastic parameters B , G , Y , σ , λ , μ , B/G , A are also calculated in same temperature range with the expressions given in literature^{11,12} using evaluated SOECs which are presented in Table 1 and Fig 2.

A perusal of Table 1 indicates that our evaluated SOECs, B , Y , G , λ , σ and A of the YM intermetallics at 300K are approximately same as given in literature¹⁻⁷. Thus, calculated SOECs of chosen compounds under

Fig. 1. SOEC vs. temperature of YZn, YCu and YAg

Table 1 – SOECs, elastic modulus and anisotropy of YM intermetallics at 300 K.

Compounds→ Parameters↓	YZn	YCu	YAg
C_{11} (GPa)	106.3 88.8 ¹ , 96.0 ⁵	109.0 121.9 ¹ , 113.6 ²	102.3 99.3 ¹ ,102.5 ² 98.3 ⁴ , 93.8 ⁶
C_{12} (GPa)	44.2 48.8 ¹ , 46.4 ⁵	51.4 49.1 ¹ 48.4 ²	40.6 54.3 ¹ , 56.6 ² 53.5 ⁴ , 48.9 ⁶
C_{44} (GPa)	48.3 48.1 ¹ 48.4 ⁵	54.6 35.7 ¹ 36.8 ²	45.0 38.5 ¹ , 37.8 ² 33.6 ⁴ , 34.4 ⁶
Y (GPa)	98.6 85.9 ¹	102.8 92.7 ¹	94.2 81.0 ¹ ,75.2 ⁴
B (GPa)	64.3 61.61 61.55	69.9 69.81 70.12	60.6 68.51,71.92 68.44,63.96
G (GPa)	39.6 33.8 ¹ , 37.1 ⁵	40.9 35.9 ¹	37.9 31.0 ¹ , 28.6 ⁴ , 29.0 ⁶
λ (GPa)	37.9	42.6	35.3
σ	0.244 0.269 ¹	0.255 0.289 ¹	0.241 0.305 ¹ ,0.317 ⁴
A	1.556 2.405 ¹	1.896 0.980 ¹	1.459 1.711 ¹ , 1.50 ⁴

potential model approach are justified. The electronic configuration of Zn,Cu and Ag are [Ar] 4s²3d¹⁰,[Ar] 4s²3d⁹ and [Kr] 3d¹⁰5s¹ respectively. The configuration shows that Cu has unfilled d sub-shell while Zn and Ag possess completely filled d sub-shell. Therefore, Cu will react more strongly with yttrium to form intermetallics than Zn and Ag. Thus, YCu is more covalent in nature as compared to YZn/Ag intermetallics. Thus, the elastic moduli of YCu intermetallics are found greater than YZn/Ag intermetallics. The compressibility and degree of stiffness of a material are directly co-related with bulk and Young moduli²⁰⁻²². The large bulk and Young moduli of YCu intermetallics in comparison to rest two intermetallics confirm that YCu possesses strong bonding strength, low compressibility, high hardness and large stiffness with respect to YZn/Ag.

Figure 1 indicates that SOECs C_{11} and C_{12} decrease while C_{44} increases with temperature for all the intermetallics under study. Thus, interatomic force in linear/axial direction decreases with temperature while it increases in transverse directions. Therefore, the interatomic forces among the atoms increase from linear to transverse direction with temperature for the chosen intermetallics. The average percent of decay in C_{11} and C_{12} of chosen intermetallics are found ~6% and ~14% respectively within the selected range of temperature while average growth in C_{44} is observed 5%. It is observed from Fig. 2 that the mechanical parameters Y , G , μ , A and G/B increase with temperature while

quantities B , λ and σ decrease with temperature. The decay in C_{11} and C_{12} causes reduction in bulk modulus with temperature while growth in C_{44} is reason behind the increase in shear modulus (G or μ) with temperature (Fig. 2). Young's modulus of $B1$ structured rare-earth monoarsenides is reported to increase with temperature²³.

Similar characteristic of Young's modulus is also obtained for YZn , YCu and YAg rare-earth intermetallics. The enhancement in parameter Y is due to increase in average elastic potential energy with temperature. The decay of B with temperature indicates that compressibility of chosen intermetallics increases with temperature.

Fig. 2. (a) B and Y vs T ; (b) G and λ vs T ; (c) σ and G/B vs T ; (d) A vs T

If toughness/fracture ratio (G/B) ≤ 0.57 or fracture/toughness ratio (B/G) ≥ 1.75 then material will be ductile^{1,23}. The value of G/B is found to increase linearly with temperature for all the three members of chosen intermetallics which reveals that brittleness or ionic nature of these materials increase with temperature. Since the room temperature values of G/B for YZn, YCu and YAg are 0.61, 0.58 and 0.62 respectively, therefore these intermetallics will show better ductility at lower temperature region. Intermetallic YCu is most ductile as it possesses large covalent nature due to vacant d sub-shell. Intermetallic YAg possesses least ductility among these three intermetallics because it has least covalent nature due to completely filled d sub-shell of Cu and half filled sub-shell. The ionic, covalent and metallic nature of bonding forces among atoms can also be recognized on the basis of Poisson's ratio. The values of Poisson's ratio of complete ionic, covalent and metallic compounds are 0, 0.25 and 0.33 respectively as well as, the bonding forces among atoms are non-central for $\sigma \sim 0-0.25$ and are central for $\sigma \sim 0.25-0.50$ ²³. The room temperature value of σ for YZn, YCu and YAg are 0.246, 0.258 and 0.243 respectively. This shows that bonding forces of YCu among these three intermetallics are more central and covalent in nature. The ionic or non-central bonding temperament of these intermetallics will increase with temperature as σ is found to decrease with temperature. The anisotropic character will increase with temperature as parameter A is found to increase with temperature (Fig. 2).

The densities of YZn, YCu and YAg intermetallics are determined with help of corresponding lattice parameter and Eq. (6) which are 5.588 gm cm⁻³, 6.016 gm cm⁻³ and 6.768 gm cm⁻³ respectively. The densities of materials Y, Zn, Cu and Ag are 4.472 gm cm⁻³, 7.14 gm cm⁻³, 8.960 gm cm⁻³ and 10.5 gm cm⁻³ respectively. Thus the density of chosen intermetallics belongs between the densities of individual materials and YCu has moderate density between YZn and YAg. It indicates that materials Zn, Cu and Ag become lighter after alloying with yttrium.

The ultrasonic velocities are evaluated using Eq. (5) for wave propagation along $\langle 100 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystallographic directions. The calculated velocities are shown in Table 2. As the C_{11} is found to be greater than C_{12} or C_{44} for all materials under study thus the longitudinal ultrasonic velocities are obtained large than that of shear ultrasonic velocity for each direction of

propagation (Table 2). Due to largest value of C_{11} and moderate density for YCu among the materials under study, the longitudinal velocity of ultrasonic wave is obtained maximum for YCu along $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction of propagation. Therefore second order elastic constants are affecting factor towards the ultrasonic velocity in YM intermetallics. Since C_{11} is decreasing while C_{44} is increasing with temperature for these YM intermetallics (Fig. 1) therefore longitudinal velocity will reduce and shear velocity will enhance with temperature in these materials. The ultrasonic wave will propagate with low hindrance and highest speed in YCu along axial direction as the Debye average velocity is obtained maximum for YCu along $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction (Table 2). Since the number of atom involved in the momentum transfer for wave propagation along axial direction is least than the non-axial direction in B2 structured materials therefore due to low energy dissipation and high stiffness along axial direction, the phonon of maximum frequency will propagate with maximum speed. This is reason for maximum V_D of YCu along $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction. Along non-axial direction, number of atom involved in propagation of wave will be large for B2 structured materials, thus density of material will play deciding role for velocity of wave. This means that the average velocity of maximum frequency of phonon will be large along non-axial direction for low density of B2 structured material. Since, YZn and YAg comprise the lowest and highest densities respectively among the chosen

Table 2 – The velocities in (km/s) and thermal relaxation time (τ) in (ps) of YM intermetallics along $\langle 100 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ directions at 300K.

Compounds→ Parameters↓	Direction	YZn	YCu	YAg
V_L	$\langle 100 \rangle$	4.342	4.257	3.888
V_S		2.912	3.013	2.579
V_D		3.139	3.226	2.786
τ		49.3	72.3	46.7
V_L	$\langle 110 \rangle$	4.658	4.735	4.148
V_{S1}		2.912	3.013	2.579
V_{S2}		2.340	2.188	2.135
V_D		2.823	2.733	2.546
τ		60.9	100.7	55.9
V_L	$\langle 111 \rangle$	4.764	4.884	4.232
V_S		2.545	2.393	2.292
V_D		2.807	2.759	2.526
τ		61.6	98.8	56.8

intermetallics therefore Debye average velocity is found maximum for YZn while minimum for YAg along non-axial directions $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ of propagation (Table 2).

The Debye temperature (T_D) are calculated using the expression given in literature¹⁷. Specific heat at constant volume (C_V) is function of T_D/T and is determined using literature^{17, 18}. Thermal relaxation time (τ), thermal conductivity (k) and Grüneisen parameter (γ) are also determined using Eqs. (7)-(9). The obtained value of T_D , C_V , k and γ are given in Table 3.

Table 3 – The Debye temperature (T_D) in (K), specific heat at constant volume C_V in ($10^5 \text{J/m}^3 \text{K}$), Grüneisen parameters (γ), thermal conductivity (k) in (W/cm K) of YM intermetallics at 300K.

Compounds→ Parameters↓	YZn	YCu	YAg
T_D	336.7	352.5	290.7
C_V	8.606	9.351	8.445
γ	0.928	0.746	0.990
κ	1.394	2.345	1.020

The temperature corresponding to maximum frequency of phonon that can propagate through crystalline media is termed as Debye temperature. Therefore, Debye temperature is directly proportional to Debye frequency ($\nu_D = V_D/\lambda_{\min}$). As V_D is found large for wave propagation along $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction therefore T_D is governed by V_D along this direction. Since V_D has maximum value for YCu therefore Debye temperature is found comparatively large for YCu with respect to YZn/Ag intermetallics. For the calculation of specific heat, the Debye temperature is required. Since T_D depends on V_D which is found to possess relatively large value for YCu than YZn/Ag intermetallics therefore, specific heat at constant volume is received high for YCu with respect to YZn/Ag intermetallics (Table 3).

High thermal conductivity is found for YCu in comparison to YZn/Ag intermetallics (Table 3). The lattice part of thermal conductivity at fixed temperature is proportional to molecular weight (M_w), cube of Debye temperature (T_D^3), atomic volume (δ^3) and γ^{-2} . The molecular weight of YZn, YCu and YAg intermetallics are 154.3 g, 152.45 g and 196.77 g respectively while volume per atom of these compounds are $2.29 \times 10^{-29} \text{m}^3$, $2.10 \times 10^{-29} \text{m}^3$ and $2.39 \times 10^{-29} \text{m}^3$ respectively.

The value of T_D^3/γ^3 is received large for YCu in comparison to YZn/Ag. Yet the molecular weight and volume per atom is maximum for YAg but thermal conductivity is maximum for YCu. Since high phonon frequency and maximum energy/momentum transfer are associated with a material having high Debye temperature and low Grüneisen parameter. Thus the thermal conductivity of these YM intermetallics are predominantly affected by Debye temperature and Grüneisen parameter.

The thermal relaxation time (τ) is directly proportional to thermal conductivity and inversely proportional to specific heat and square of Debye average velocity. The τ is obtained minimum along axial directions $\langle 100 \rangle$ and maximum along non-axial direction $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ in chosen YM intermetallics. The maximum value of V_D in chosen intermetallics along axial direction is reason for minimum value of τ along this direction. Hence, the direction dependent thermal relaxation time is highly affected with the Debye average velocity. Along a particular direction of propagation of wave, the thermal conductivities of YM intermetallics are dominating factor towards the thermal relaxation as for each directions of propagation of ultrasonic waves, τ received minimum in YAg and maximum in YCu intermetallics. The value of τ in chosen YM intermetallics is found in between 46ps to 100ps. The value of τ for metals/rare-earth metals/semi-metals/alloys and semiconductors are reported to be $<16\text{ps}$ and $>16\text{ps}$ respectively^{10,24-26}. The reported value of τ for B1 structured rare-earth monoarsenides^{23/} polonides²⁷ are in range 7ps-16ps. Therefore rare earth compounds can have thermal relaxation time up to 100ps depending upon their thermal conductivity. Furthermore, these YM compounds possess high thermal relaxation time in comparison to metals/alloys and semiconductors. Since, the ultrasonic attenuation at high temperature is caused by phonon-phonon interaction and thermo-elastic relaxation mechanism, which is proportional to thermal relaxation time/thermal conductivity²⁷⁻²⁹ therefore these YM intermetallics shall have relatively high loss of ultrasonic energy in comparison to loss in semi-conductors.

Conclusions

On the basis of above discussion we conclude that our potential model approach for evaluation of SOECs is justified for YM intermetallics. Significant high value of bulk and Young moduli of YCu intermetallics in

comparison to YZn/Ag intermetallics substantiate that YCu possesses strong bonding strength, low compressibility, high hardness and large stiffness with respect to YZn/Ag. As the physical quantities C_{11} , C_{12} , B , λ and σ are found to decay with temperature while C_{44} , Y , G , μ and A are received to enhance with temperature therefore brittleness or ionic nature of these materials increase with temperature. Hence, these YM intermetallics will represent superior ductility at lower temperature region. The reduction in density of materials Zn, Cu and Ag is found after alloying with Yttrium. Second order elastic constants play dominating role towards the ultrasonic velocity in YM intermetallics. Elastic moduli, ultrasonic velocity, thermal conductivity and thermal relaxation time of YCu intermetallics are found greater than YZn/Ag intermetallics thus elastic, ultrasonic and thermal behaviour of YCu intermetallics will be better than YZn/Ag intermetallics. The obtained results provide a good understanding of elastic, mechanical, thermal and ultrasonic properties of chosen YM intermetallics that may be used for further investigation and also in material manufacturing industries.

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